

Building a Secure Bootloader: Considerations and Recommendations

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Abstract. As the number of so-called Internet-of-Things is continuously rising and the urge for regular hardware updates has never been higher, the security of our smart objects all around us is often skipped due to lack of development time. By default, these devices are equipped with a primitive bootloader, which is executing code located at a designated address. Within this document, we are describing a simple but worthwhile validation mechanism, which is realized by using digital signature algorithm included in the bootloader. As a result, we are making sure that no malicious code or malware can be executed and the running application is originating from a trusted and known developer. Nevertheless, even the strongest cryptographic system cannot ensure the highest possible security, if the device itself is prone to fault injection attacks. A simple alteration of the voltage or clock speed is sufficient in order to unsettle the device's usual and intended behaviour and cause instruction skipping among others. At worst, this could result in bypassing of authentication mechanisms, one of the most common targets of an attack. With the aid of randomly-chosen delays in instruction processing as well as multiple use of authentication mechanisms, we are describing straightforward mechanisms in order to decrease the level of success of common fault injections. Moreover, a list of recommendations is given in this document suitable for situations, where resources are limited and no additional hardware can be added.

Keywords: Bootloader, Internet-of-Things, resource-constrained, security, embedded, fault injection

1 Introduction & Motivation

Every day we interact with a lot of objects equipped with technology, which are interconnected via the internet. Such an interaction is often even unobvious for the user. These objects, nowadays better known as Internet-of-Things or short IoT, acting as the daily companion, aim to support us in various activities, such as the control of the light bulbs and temperature setting of the smart home, monitoring of vital parameters for better health or be present in today's cars backing us in moving seamlessly in the traffic. Besides these end-user application domains, the need within the industry for smart objects is raising as well.

Inventory tracking, machine managing, cost saving and efficiency increase are just a few applications that result in the IoT devices being mostly used outside of the smart home environment.

As early as 2006, the IoT world consisted of 6 billion objects, and it has grown to 15 billion until 2015. Next year, it is prognosticated that there will be around 200 billion of smart devices out there, which leads to 26 IoT objects for every human being on earth. [1]

The urge for regularly providing new hardware to the market, forces the manufacturers to a reduction of development time. Shortcomings in the development phase lead in turn to a reduction of the security level. Resulting, important security features are integrated only to a limited extent or (in worst case) excluded completely from the devices. Paying insufficient amount of attention on security results in drastic consequences. Imagine, millions of devices have to be returned back to the manufacturer due to a vulnerability exploited when the device was already deployed on the market without any or only low-level security measures.

Our Contributions: With the help of this document, we are summarizing the basic principle and functionality of a state-of-the-art bootloader and describing the minimal expenses, which are necessary to enable application image validation based on Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm and hence harden the overall system's security. As fault injections are often used to bypass such validation processes, we first shed a light on the most common fault injections, in order to underline the importance of the listed set of recommendations.

Paper Outline: In Chapter 2 we first describe the state-of-the-art bootloader process as well as its aim and the minimum set of functionality. For a better comprehension, further details with regards to process handling on a Microcontroller are given in this chapter as well. Based on the default bootloader design, we are providing an approach in order to enable application validation by means of a secure bootloader in Chapter 3. As the security can be increased to a limited extend only, in Chapter 5 we are listing a set of recommendations in order to exterminate common attacks or at least minimize the level of their success. For a better understanding of the listed recommendations, we are summarizing several attacks and fault risks the chapter before, in Chapter 4. Finally, we are providing a conclusion of this document in Chapter 6.

2 State-of-the-Art Bootloader Analysis

The underlying hardware of Internet of Things is a microcontroller, short MCU, based in most cases on either an 8-bit or a 32-bit architecture, depending on the final application field. Invented decades ago, the 8-bit architecture is the most used processor architecture. While 8-bit is used for embedded applications executing simple instructions, 32-bit-based devices are used for more powerful operations as they are able to process four byte at once as well as perform graph-

ical processes used in multimedia systems. However, powerful microcontrollers with complex architectures are not offering advantages only. If a device has to run for months, years or even a decade on a single battery cell, an 8-bit controller is preferred as far as the end-application allows.

So, what does the bootloader do for us? In the context of microcontrollers, a bootloader is actually the first piece of code, which runs right after a power-up/device reset. Thus, bootloader runs before any other user application stored in the memory. Roughly speaking, a default bootloader offers only two jobs: executing an installed application located in device's non-volatile memory (NVM) or replacing the installed application by a new one. During each power-up sequence, the bootloader is listening, such as on the serial port, for a certain amount of time. If a dedicated signal, respectively the programming command¹ was recognized, the bootloader will initialize the download of the image (from the programmer tool) followed by a flashing process with respect to NVM. In case there was no command received, the application's instructions will be loaded and executed, which are located at a particular (pre-defined) memory location, in the so-called reset vector (RV). By default, the start-up procedure/instruction handling on a MCU looks as follows:

1. The hardware is being initialized and the CPU fetches the initial instruction using the Reset Vector (RV)², which will be executed first.
2. The bootloader (if present) is entered and initialized. Resulting, a basic subset of peripherals is loaded, which is necessary to process bootloader's instructions. Among others, this includes the system clock, interrupt service routines, a peripheral for communication and a task scheduler, which are necessary for a communication with the programmer tool and modification of its environment (loading new software, etc.).
3. The bootloader listens for a certain amount of time for dedicated commands. If a command (or list of commands) was received, the command(s) will be executed, followed by a soft reset of the system.
4. The main user application is executed, accordingly to the fetch-decode-execute principle:
 - (a) FETCH: read instruction from address on which the program counter is pointing and increase program counter
 - (b) DECODE: convert fetched instruction into CPU-readable code
 - (c) EXECUTE: execute fetched decoded instruction

The said procedure and the boot-up process is depicted in Figure 1.

¹ A default bootloader is equipped with some basic commands. All, respectively almost all commands aim to modify the environment, such as write or erase the memory, as well as read environment's memory. In addition to these two basic commands, a default bootloader should be able to perform a (soft) reboot in order to enter the user application. [3]

² The reset vector (RV) is the location in memory where the first instruction for the bootloader/application is located. When a processor is started up it begins program execution at the address stored in the reset vector. [3]

Fig. 1. Generally-used boot process

However, most of the microcontroller processors are based on the Harvard- or Von-Neumann-Architecture and hence the CPU is pipelined. As a result of pipelining, the fetch-decode-execute procedure will happen simultaneously. To be more accurate, while the first instruction is already in the execution stage, the second instruction is being decoded and the third instruction fetched, and so on.

Fig. 2. Instruction pipelining accordingly to fetch-decode-execute principle

A bootloader is not mandatory, since the initial application could be uploaded to the device by means of an In-System Programmer (ISP). However, as a consequence of having no bootloader on the device, no updates of the application code can be made. Having the possibility to update the device in turn is necessary to close security gaps as soon as they are discovered. Since a bootloader is equipped with enough permissions to be able to update the application and write new instructions into the flash, it is representing a very common and attractive attack surface.

3 Secure Bootloader: Design

In order to make sure no (malicious) alteration of the software happened, a secure bootloader is unavoidable. The secure bootloader is tasked with ensuring validity of the application image it is executing. In other words, the main purpose of the secure bootloader is to prevent running of malicious code or malware. In many cases the bootloader possesses highly sensible information and is acting as a Root-of-Trust, the upmost immutable component of a system, which can be always trusted. In addition, as already discussed, a bootloader is provided with all permissions necessary for modifying the system's environment. Due to these facts, the bootloader is indeed a common target for the attacker. So, how does the proposed secure boot process differ from the usual one?

The first steps of the secure bootloader are just as discussed in Chapter 2, respectively depicted in Figure 1 with regards to a default boot process. Once the device has started, the bootloader (1st stage) performs hardware initializations and loads required data from memory. Further, it listens for a pre-defined set of commands (if not disabled). Instead of just executing the installed application, the 2nd stage bootloader is initialized and executed. As a result, the bootloader loads further data from the memory. Using this data the bootloader determines and selects the start address of the active image (main application) that needs to be validated. After a successful validation of the application signature using the hardcoded and securely stored key, the bootloader will jump to the image start address and execute the application. In case of validation failure, the bootloader will first check if the restore flag has been set. If so, the image start address will be set to the former image (resp. previous firmware version), the restore flag unset and a reboot performed. In this way we ensure robustness of proposed approach in case of maliciously modified or corrupted updates and provide rollback mechanism for failed updates. In case that the restore flag is not set and validation has failed, the device will refuse to run the application and stop working.

In the following, we are presenting the working flow of our proposed secure bootloader process. As it can be seen in the figure below, we highlighted the changes to the default boot process in **green** colour. Further, we depicted the rollback mechanism in **gray** colour, as this is optional and does not increase the level of security, but provides a backup.

Fig. 3. Updated boot process with application image validation

3.1 Technical Details on Proposed Design

In order to ensure a certain level of security, the proposed secure bootloader design and its validation procedure is based on the Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm (ECDSA). In our current implementation, we have selected the SECP256R1 curve, which provides 128 bits of security, comparable to RSA 3072. The elliptic curve approach has been selected due to shorter key length, which

is more suitable for space-constrained embedded devices. If a higher level of security is needed the implementation can be trivially changed to elliptic curve of larger size. The (hardcoded) public key, stored in secure environment and used for signature validation is assumed to be added during the device enrolment phase and already present on the device. The validation of a signature based on the ECDSA ensures that any data corruption on the board, malicious or accidental, will be detected and that any modified application will be prevented from booting.

As it will be discussed later, hardcoding secret keys doesn't increase (if not located in a secure key storage) the overall security of the system. Alternatively to hardcoded keys, so-called Physical Unclonable Function (PUF) based on SRAM (Static Random-Access Memory) could be used in order to obtain a unique key, which is tied to the device and cannot be reproduced. The usage of a SRAM PUF comes only at the cost of reserving a small amount of SRAM space (less than 1KB) for calculating a 256-bit unique device key, making it feasible even for resource-constrained devices. SRAM PUFs are based on the fact that uninitialized SRAM memory, due to small physical variations during the production process, has random start values. Based on readings of these values in uninitialized state it is possible to uniquely identify a device in question. The variations introduced during the production cannot be controlled by the manufacturer, hence making them unclonable. [4]

4 Secure Bootloader: Considerations

For a better comprehension of the list of recommendations, which is provided in the next chapter, in the following we are going into details on common attack scenarios as well as faults, which are applied in order to gain access or change the device's behaviour.

In principle, we distinguish between three different types of attacks: non-invasive, semi-invasive and invasive attacks. [11,12] While non-invasive attacks are relatively easy to apply as there are no (hardware) modifications on the target necessary, invasive and semi-invasive attacks are costly and require specialized tools to be successful. More precisely, a non-invasive attack is applied without any physical harm, e.g. by altering the power source, clock signal or environmental temperature either below or above their usual limitations. As stated, invasive and semi-invasive attacks require much more budget (compared to non-invasive) as well as time and knowledge. In that case, there are almost no limitations in performing these attacks, as an attacker applying an invasive attack isn't backed off modifying the target, like adding new wires and connections, while taking the risk to completely destroy the device. On the other hand, for a semi-invasive attack "only" the chip is depackaged in order to be able to probe single connections. The most common attack goal on a MCU is to cause misbehaviour aiming to bypass security features and/or obtain sensitive data. This type of an attack is better known as fault injection, which implies the manipulation of

the system's environment by applying different principles. [2] The most popular fault injections are realized by means of:

- **Power manipulation:** Manipulation of the target's power source, respectively a (very fast) alteration of the voltage, results in instruction skipping. [5] Performing a voltage drop (turning rapidly power off and on again) allows to affect only parts of the MCU. To be more specific, a rapid voltage drop may cause power loss in the CPU, while the volatile memory still retains its values. With respect to required resources and tools, this method is the most effective compared to the following fault injection techniques. Voltage alteration is a non-invasive attack. [14,2,15]
- **Clock manipulation:** Since the clock represents the time base of the whole system and is crucial for the timing of process handling, a simple manipulation (adjustment of speed) of this source may result in instruction skipping as the processor and the circuit are not synchronized to each other in terms of timing. With respect to required resources and tools, this method is relatively easy to realize. However, clock manipulation is only effective for targets with an external clock source. Clock alteration is a non-invasive attack. [7,15]
- **Temperature fluctuation:** A device behaves as specified if the surrounding temperature conditions are complied and within the lower and upper thresholds set by the manufacturer. However, if these thresholds are exceeded, the device gets more vulnerable to fault injections, as the timeframe for glitches increases. As a consequence, instructions can be repeated or random instructions introduced as well as the opcode of instructions changed. Further, as soon as a chip reaches a certain temperature (below or above its pre-defined thresholds), the way how to access the memory might change, resulting in functioning write operations only while no reading operations possible and vice versa. Alteration of the surrounding temperature is a non-invasive attack. [8]
- **Electromagnetic emission:** Applying electromagnetic induction in, for example, transistors might cause logic failures and unexpected behaviour. As parts of a processor, like the transistor, are based on closed circuit loops, a magnetic field induction, respectively the induction of current might disturb the said circuits' intended workflow. Electromagnetic emission injection is a non-invasive attack (in case of a metal-shield/package of the chip, this attack would be classified as a semi-invasive attack since the shielding has to be removed first). [6,9]
- **Light injection:** Similar to electromagnetic induction, an intense light or a laser beam might cause failures in electric circuits as well. While doing so, the current is induced by photons, so a similar effect, as described above, can be realized. In addition, ultra-violet (UV) light is also known for erasing floating-gate transistor-based components, such as One-Time Programmable (OTP), flash or Electrically Erasable Programmable Read-Only Memories (EEPROM). Optical injections are semi-invasive attacks as the target chip has to be depackaged. [13,10]

As it can be seen in the listing above, all fault injections described above are aiming on either instruction skipping or instruction modification. Skipping or modifying of instructions leads to a broad range of attacks. While skipping of instructions alters the intended behavior without altering any memory content, modification of instructions goes further aiming to allow the attacker to upload malware (or similar). Consequently, an instruction skip might result in bypassing secure authentication or verification algorithm, while instruction modification might allow the attacker to re-use the device for other (unintended) purpose.

5 Secure Bootloader: List of Recommendations

Following the approach on the secure bootloader presented in Chapter 3, it is ensured that only valid application code is executed, and no malicious code can be bypassed. Nevertheless, such a design is still vulnerable to physical fault injections, as listed in Chapter 4. As the protection against these fault injections is only achievable by using additional (dedicated) hardware (which is mostly not present on common MCUs), in the following we are focusing on mechanisms, which are at least hardening the exploitation of vulnerabilities. As a result of this, these mechanisms are raising the required time (as well as costs) to gain the knowledge of the system and obtain useful information, which in turn decreases the attacker's interest on such a device.

- **Random delays:** As presented in Chapter 4, the most popular fault injection techniques are aiming on instruction skipping. In order to be successful in this manner, the right timing is essential. As a result of this, the target device needs to be monitored for a while to observe data, such as the voltage consumption or similar. Based on this data, the attacker will estimate the spot, where to glitch, respectively by dropping the voltage for a moment for example. Since cryptographic algorithms are heavy with regards to power consumption, the right point is usually easily determined and as a consequence an authentication mechanism is bypassed. However, if randomly selected delays are incorporated in the usual process, the estimation of the right timing is made difficult and it gets hard(er) for the attacker to "guess" where to glitch.
- **Dummy cycles:** Similar to the principle of random delays are dummy cycles. In order to sophisticate the target's behaviour in the eyes of the attacker, dummy functions or superfluous loops in the usual process are introduced, which pose certain challenges to the attacker, aiming on hardening the estimation of the right timing as well.
- **Redundancy:** Another mechanism in the domain of hardening the behaviour analysis is the creation of redundancy. As discussed earlier, instruction skipping is commonly aimed and used for bypassing authentication mechanisms. A simple increase of the authentication, validation and verification cycles, will harden the device against a potential bypass. Resulting, the attacker has to perform successful multiple glitches in a single run to achieve a bypass.

- **Built-in features:** As simple as it sounds, the use of built-in features increases the security a lot. Most common devices, even labelled as resource-constrained devices, are often equipped with functionality like Memory Protection Unit (MPU) in order to restrict the access of specific memory sections. Often unused or even unknown, the MPU offers modes where only execution of instructions (read permission) and no modifications (write permission) are allowed, which helps to reduce the risk of uploading malware to the target.
- **Avoid master key:** Equally obvious as the predecessor recommendation is the avoidance of using hardcoded keys or master keys provided within the system. Often left unencrypted in the memory, such keys are easily obtained by the attacker. Further, if the master key is used for decryption of the application image, it opens the attacker the door for reverse-engineering of application and possibly identification of additional vulnerabilities usable to exploit device.
- **Internal components:** Since we are considering fault injections, further physical access needs to be taken into account as well. When using external components, such as external memory module for outsourcing data, consideration has to be made to keep sensitive information internal to the MCU (considering the bus system). If the outsourced code represents parts of your intellectual property, external components should be avoided completely.
- **Monitoring:** The last recommendation is considering the monitoring of inconsistencies of the device's environment. To be more specific, this recommendation is focused on the monitoring of the power source (voltage drops or inconsistent power source), the surrounding temperature (temperature differs from usual known values) and applied light (external light emitted). However, this kind of monitoring is only possible, if the corresponding sensors, such as temperature and light sensors are present and the power source is measurable.

Combining already the first three mechanisms listed above introducing random delays, dummy cycles and redundant checks, will harden your system and decrease the level of success of attackers, so that the effectiveness of fault injections is virtually zero. In other words, let's imagine that random delays and cycles as well as redundancy were integrated: the attacker aims to obtain the right timing when the authentication takes place in order to bypass this step, for instance, by means of dropping the voltage. Since the behaviour varies after each restart, the right timing is hard to estimate. Additionally, dummy cycles are hardening the situation further. Lastly, even if the attacker managed to guess the glitch point, there are still redundant checks performed, resulting in a challenge, where certain instructions need to be skipped in order to bypass any security features.

However, theoretically seen, the above-discussed mechanisms are only challenging the attacker and delaying the success of a fault injection, but not eliminating them at all, since most of the mechanisms are realized in software only.

Consequently, in order to enable tamper protection, dedicated hardware is necessary.

6 Conclusion and Summary

In a world with nearly 26 IoT devices per every human being on earth, it becomes apparent that these smart objects are all around us as our daily companions in many different cases, whether we like it or not. Due to lack of development time, the manufacturers are forced to release new hardware without paying attention on the security of the said devices. However, skipping the security might result in vulnerabilities from various perspectives. Imagine, millions of devices having to be returned due to a vulnerability exploited in the field. Also, discovered vulnerabilities by malicious attackers might harm the user, when used in safety-related applications or in controlling the smart home and its security system for example.

Within this document, we have presented an update of the default boot procedure in order to enable application image validation. As a consequence, only validated applications can be executed, hence no malicious code nor malware can be placed on the device unrecognized. Nevertheless, even the strongest cryptographic algorithm is worth nothing, when the device is prone to fault injection attacks.

As demonstrated, these fault injections are easily performed causing misbehaviour resulting in bypassing security mechanisms such as validations or authentications. As a result, we summarized a set of recommendations in order to harden the analysis of the device's behaviour and in turn decrease the level of success of fault injections.

Finally, it needs to be said that such mechanisms are practically interfering the attacker's attempts. However, having an infinite number of resources, it is only a matter of time to inject successfully faults and cause misbehaviour on the device again.

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